

Pharmacophore mapping and virtual screening for the identification of new PPAR γ agonists

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Pharmacophore mapping using a DISCO-based method and virtual screening using molecular docking was employed to identify new leads as anti-hyperglycemic agents for the target PPAR γ . Three pharmacophoric queries were generated, validated, and submitted for virtual screening of commercial databases like NCI, Maybridge, and Lead Quest with a total of 330,989 compounds. The resulting hits were passed through hierarchical virtual filters for data reduction and subsequently docked in the active site of PPAR γ using a FlexX-based docking program. The hits exhibiting better FlexX scores than the reference ligand, rosiglitazone, were analyzed in terms of their binding mode in the active site. This study resulted in the identification of new and interesting structural chemotypes capable of fostering interaction like rosiglitazone in the PPAR γ binding pocket and hence can be further followed for experimental validation.

Keywords: Pharmacophore mapping, virtual screening, docking, PPAR γ .

Introduction

Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor (PPAR) family of receptors belong to the nuclear receptor family of transcription factors. PPARs are one of the most critical targets for the treatment of type-II diabetes¹. Out of the three PPAR subtypes (PPAR- α , - β and - γ), PPAR γ is the prime target which is involved in the process of insulin sensitization resulting from the binding of specific agonists. Insulin sensitization occurs due to inhibition of the expression of a wide range of cytokines like TNF α ². Different chemotypes of molecules have been found to possess PPAR γ agonistic activity, these include glitazones³⁻⁶ (thiazolidinediones-TZD containing compounds), oxazolidinediones⁷, isoxazolidinediones⁸, propionic acid derivatives^{9,10}, tyrosine derivatives¹¹⁻¹³, tetrazoles¹⁴ and many more¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Most of these agonists have evolved from a common scaffold by replacements in the three critical structural units, namely (a) acidic-head group,

(b) central-aromatic linker, and (c) steric side chain, as depicted in Fig. S1. Dual and pan PPAR agonists, with the added advantage of curing hyperglycemia as well as hypertriglyceridemia, have also been developed²⁰⁻²³. In addition to diabetes, the role of PPAR agonists is also being investigated in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease²⁴, cancer²⁵, cardiovascular disorders²⁶, dermatology²⁷, and autoimmune disorders²⁸. Due to the multi-faceted application of these molecules, novel PPAR agonists with low potential of toxicity are being pursued. In this context, computer-aided drug design methods²⁹ such as pharmacophore mapping³⁰, virtual screening³¹, molecular docking³², and quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR)³³ may help in the identification of hit/leads in a short timeframe. In continuation of work related to the design and synthesis of PPAR agonists^{15,16,34-38}, we hereby report virtual screening assisted discovery of potential PPAR agonists with some innovative 'acidic fragments'.

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Experimental

Selection of molecules:

Three pharmacophore queries **P0**, **P1** and **P2** were obtained from a set of nine PPAR γ agonists. A broad query **P0** was designed from a mix of cyclic and acyclic agonists. More specific queries **P1** and **P2** were developed solely from the cyclic and acyclic systems, respectively. The co-crystallized bioactive conformation of ligands was extracted from the ternary complex and minimized by simple minimization using Powel method³⁹ with the termination gradient of 0.05 kcal/mol Å employing Tripos force fields⁴⁰ within the constraints of 100 iterations. Constraint minimization was required to maintain the U-shaped binding conformation. These molecules were then minimized using semi-empirical AM1⁴¹ forcefields of MOPAC software interfaced with SYBYL6.9 molecular modeling package⁴². The non-crystallized ligands were minimized by the AM1 method maintaining the putative bioactive conformations.

Pharmacophore generation, validation, and virtual screening:

Pharmacophore models were generated using the DISCO module⁴³ of SYBYL6.9 using bioactive conformations of the ligands. A given DISCO run provides many pharmacophoric models to be used as queries for virtual screening. Validation of the models was carried out using PPAR-DB1 database with known and diverse, active, and inactive PPAR γ agonists. It contained a total of 276 compounds with varying levels of activities. Additionally, a decoy database non-PPAR-DB2 consisting of 500 structurally diverse PPAR γ unrelated compounds was generated for cross-validation. A reliable model should choose active PPAR γ agonists from PPAR-DB1 and discard molecules from the decoy dataset.

Three commercial databases NCI (National Cancer Institute), Maybridge (MB), and Leadquest (LQ) were used for virtual screening. NCI databank had 234,055, Maybridge had 55,541, and the Leadquest had 41,393 compounds (all implemented in Unity4.4⁴⁴ module of SYBYL6.9). The broad **P0** query was used as the first filter for screening. The hits obtained were segregated into cyclic and acyclic acidic types by employing queries **P1** and **P2**. Lipinski's rule of five⁴⁵ (Ro5) with one deviation was allowed, and van der Waals bumps checks were adopted as the subsequent hierarchical filters.

Molecular docking:

Docking studies were carried out using FlexX program³⁹. For the cyclic systems docking was carried out in the rosiglitazone binding pocket of PPAR γ (PDB ID 2PRG) while farglitazar binding pocket (PDB ID 1FM9) was used for docking of acyclic systems. Active site was defined as the area within 6.5 Å around co-crystallized ligand with customization done for histidine, serine, and tyrosine residues to represent reported H-bonds. Formal charges were assigned to all the molecules. Candidates with scores better than rosiglitazone were considered for estimation of G_score, PMF_score, D_score and Chem_score using CSCORE module⁴⁷ of SYBYL6.9

Results and discussion

Pharmacophore mapping:

To obtain new starting points for PPAR γ agonist activity, initially, two different datasets were chosen for the generation of **P0** pharmacophore. The first dataset consisted of four representative molecules selected from each chemotype of the known PPAR γ agonists to represent diversity, namely rosiglitazone (from 2PRG), farglitazar (from 1FM9), JTT-501 (isoxazolidinedione derivative), and a tetrazole derivative (Fig. 1). The second set of five molecules consisted of PPAR γ agonists for which the bioactive conformation was known from the cocrystal structures with PPAR γ (2PRG, 1FM9, 1KNU, 1NYX, and 1I7G), four with the open-chain acidic head groups and rosiglitazone with the cyclic acidic part. DISCO analysis was carried using the bioactive U-shaped conformation. Based on the literature reports and visual inspection of different PPAR γ chemotypes, common pharmacophore features were identified: (i) 1-2 acceptor atoms in the acidic unit, with the corresponding 2-4 receptor donor sites, (ii) a donor atom corresponding to the acidic hydrogen donor with its corresponding acceptor site on the receptor, (iii) a central aromatic ring centroid with variable distance tolerance range depending upon the linker length, (iv) a hydrophobic center, (v) a possible acceptor atom for the ethereal oxygen atom and its corresponding donor site on the receptor and (vi) side chain features arising from the polar nitrogen or oxygen-containing groups (Fig. S2). DISCO runs were undertaken for both the datasets with rosiglitazone template as opted by DISCO module, first with default and later with modified set-

Fig. 1. Important PPAR γ agonists considered for the development of pharmacophore maps.

tings. Queries were generated from the best models from both the sets (Tables S1, S2). Upon validation of queries against PPAR-DB1, the best results were obtained from the query **P0** (Fig. S3, Table 1) with 7 features at a tolerance of 1.5 Å that picked up most of the actives and discarded many of the inactives.

To further improve the hit rate and reduce the number of false positives, two separate queries were generated for cyclic and acyclic acid fragments. **P1** was developed from five compounds with cyclic acidic head groups, TZD derivative (rosiglitazone), isoxazolidinedione derivative (JTT-501), oxazolidinedione derivative, oxadiazolidinedione derivative, and tetrazole derivative. The optimization of DISCO runs resulted in **P1** (Table S3) that picked up most of the molecules containing cyclic acidic moieties (Fig. S4, Table 1).

Similarly, the **P2** query was developed from farglitazar, ragaglitazar, tesaglitazar, and carbazole derivative all with acyclic acidic head groups (Fig. 1). These molecules were aligned with ragaglitazar as the template. Optimization of DISCO runs led to query **P2** (Table S4) that picked up most

Table 1. The details of pharmacophoric maps **P0**, **P1** and **P2**

Query	Molecules ¹	Tolerance (Å)	No. of features	Actives [@]	Inactives [#]
P0	5	1.5	7	261	14
P1	4	2.5	13	173	3
P2	5	0.5–3.00	7	94	0

¹Number of molecules chosen for the generation of queries (refer Fig. 1). [@]Number of active molecules picked up (out of 276) by various queries. [#]Number of inactive molecules picked up (out of 17) by multiple queries.

of the acyclic acid derivatives from the database PPAR-DB1 (Fig. S5, Table 1).

Virtual screening:

Thus, three pharmacophore queries (**P0**, **P1**, and **P2**) were finalized based on their ability to discard the inactives from the databases. Further, cross-validation was carried out by screening these queries against the non-PPAR-DB2, or the decoy set. The **P0**, being a broad query, was used as the first filter step to search the three databases. The hits obtained were further segregated towards achieving cyclic and acyclic systems using **P1** and **P2**. The next hierarchical filters that were employed to bring down the number of hits further were the Lipinski's Ro5, van der Waals bumps (VB), and limit number of rotatable of bonds (NRB) to 15. The number of molecules obtained as hits at each stage of hierarchical filtration is shown in a schematic diagram of the virtual screening strategy, given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Virtual screening statistics of databases NCI, Maybridge and Leadquest.

Molecular docking studies:

Molecular docking studies were performed on two pro-

tein cocrystal structures of PPAR γ , 2PRG, and 1FM9. Molecules obtained from the virtual screening of query **P1** were docked in the active site of 2PRG having rosiglitazone as bound ligand while those obtained from query **P2** were docked in the active site of 1FM9 with bound Farglitazar. The docking scores were compared to that of rosiglitazone as the standard having obtained the FlexX score of -31.4 kcal/mol. A total of 1348 hits were docked in the active site of 2PRG. Out of 1180 successfully docked molecules, 52 molecules scored better than rosiglitazone. 533 hits obtained from the virtual screening of the second query **P2** were docked in the active site of 1FM9, of these 300 molecules got successfully docked, and 19 scored better than rosiglitazone. The CSCORE analysis was carried out for all the molecules scoring better than rosiglitazone. The molecules were ranked according to their performance in all the five scoring functions (FlexX, G_Score, PMF_Score, D_Score, Chem_Score) in comparison to the corresponding scores of Rosiglitazone (Table S5).

Lead identification:

The final hits obtained from the virtual screening study were analyzed in terms of their chemical novelty and diversity in acidic fragments, central aromatic region, and side chains. Critical analyses led to the categorization of the new hits as (a) molecules having a Y-shaped structure, (b) symmetrical molecules, and (c) molecules having unique functional head groups.

The active site of PPAR γ has been described to be Y-shaped. However, most of the known ligands are labeled as U-shaped (rosiglitazone in 2PRG). To accommodate the two facts, it can be considered as μ -shaped (Fig. 3) with (i) arm A where acidic unit binds, (ii) arm B where the central hydrophobic group binds, (iii) arm C with the tail portion of glitazones, (iv) arm D with empty space in both 2PRG and 1FM9 and (v) arm E with the benzoyl phenyl of Farglitazar in 1FM9. From the current screening, several compounds were identified which occupy arms B, C, D, and partially occupy arm A. These compounds may be labeled as Y-shaped compounds. Fig. S6 shows the representative examples belonging to this set, and Fig. S7 shows the active site with one such example. Y-shaped molecules are ideal for performing lead optimization, which has a probability of showing good

binding affinity. All these molecules showed better docking scores than rosiglitazone.

Interestingly, the better scores were not due to better binding in the acidic fragment (arm A, Fig. 3) but due to tight binding in the three arms B, C and D. However, it is known that the interaction of acidic moiety of PPAR γ ligands with residues His449, Tyr473, His323, and Ser289 plays a crucial role in the activation of PPAR γ . Thus, these molecules may not activate the receptor, but since these showed a strong binding affinity for the receptor, they may act as antagonists. It would be imperative to study such compounds as specific antagonists of a receptor subtype that may be useful to address the problems of receptor-subtype selectivity.

Fig. 3. Proposed μ -shaped cavity of PPAR γ .

The second category of hits were found to have quasi-C2 symmetry (Fig. S8). One of the molecules bound to the active site is shown in Fig. S9. These hits could be further classified as (i) those with identical units hooked to form a dimeric molecule and (ii) those in which the same interacting group was present at two ends of a common central portion. Both types of symmetrical molecules would have double the chances of interaction with gain in potency.

A large number of hits were categorized based on their novelty in acidic functional head groups. Besides H-bonding to His323, Tyr473, His449, and Ser289, they showed addi-

tional interactions with Gln286, Tyr327. An important set of newly identified head groups is given in Fig. S10. One of the molecules is shown in its active site in Fig. S11.

Various aliphatic potential bridging linkers between the acidic units and the side chains were observed in the hits obtained like amides, urea derivatives, hydrazine derivatives, carbonyl systems, dicarbonyl systems contrary to the notion that an aromatic bridging group is vital according to the earlier observations.

Following the virtual screening exercise, a literature search was carried out to verify whether such units have been reported earlier. Xu *et al.* have explored GW2433 as a Y-shaped ligand for PPAR δ ⁴⁶. Sauerberg *et al.* defined a set of dimeric systems with almost C2 symmetry as PPAR γ agonists⁴⁸. A few derivatives of cinnamic acid have also been reported as PPAR α/γ dual agonists⁴⁹. These examples further validate the results obtained from this study.

Conclusions

In summary, we developed and validated three pharmacophore models using a diverse set of PPAR γ agonists using DISCO program. The models were then used for virtual screening of chemical databases. The broad query **P0** resulted in a total of 17,822 hits that were subsequently filtered using more specific queries **P1** and **P2**. Filters like Lipinski's Ro5 and van der Waal bumps were further applied to reduce the number of hits that were subsequently docked into the PPAR γ binding pocket using FlexX program. Of the 75% successfully docked systems, 71 molecules scored better than the reference molecule, rosiglitazone.

Further prioritization was done with respect to the five different scoring functions in CSCORE. This work provided several new scaffolds categorized as (i) Y-shaped, (ii) quasi-C2 symmetrical and (iii) systems with new functional head groups. The confidence in this work further increased after noticing examples of these new scaffolds in the literature reports^{46,48,49}. Further experimental validation of these novel scaffolds hold high promise in identifying new agents to treat insulin resistance.

Supporting Information

The supporting information contains additional figures and tables mentioned in the text.

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